

Experimental study on a thermochemical energy storage system for water heating with microchannel flat tube heat exchangers

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ABSTRACT

Integrating open thermochemical energy storage (TCES) with domestic central heating system remains challenging due to differences in heat transfer media. To overcome these, two distinct TCES system configurations for water heating were previously developed: one incorporating a detached finned microchannel heat exchanger (DFHEX-TCES) and another utilizing an internal bare microchannel heat exchanger (IBHEX-TCES), both validated through simulation. In this study, a versatile TCES experimental platform was developed to evaluate and compare these configurations under various operating conditions. Results demonstrated that while both single-layer configurations achieved comparable peak water temperature lifts, the DFHEX-TCES significantly outperformed the IBHEX-TCES by maintaining temperature lifts for approximately 1.5 times longer. At a low airflow rate ($17 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$), both reactors reached peak temperature lifts around $5.7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, but DFHEX-TCES maintained lifts above $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ nearly twice as long. Increasing airflow to $34 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ enhanced the DFHEX-TCES peak temperature lift to approximately $9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and extended the duration to nearly 90 min, roughly triple that of IBHEX-TCES under identical conditions. Furthermore, adopting a multilayer DFHEX-TCES extended this duration by more than twofold. This study demonstrates the practical feasibility of DFHEX-TCES for domestic water heating and highlights the advantages of the multilayer modular design in enhancing thermal performance.

1. Introduction

As global economies recover from pandemic lockdowns, the prices of fossil fuels have begun to rise globally, further exacerbated by regional conflicts, leading to an unprecedented energy crisis in European countries [1,2]. In these nations, over 80 % of residential energy consumption is for heating, with approximately 60 % dependent on fossil fuels [3, 4]. The current energy crisis has left nearly 6 million households in the UK facing fuel shortages and living under severe cold conditions [5]. Solar energy, characterized by its extensive distribution, low acquisition cost, and environmental sustainability, has emerged as one of the most promising solutions to the current energy shortage [6]. However, the inherent characteristics of solar energy, such as temporal intervals, spatial dispersion, and intensity fluctuations, present challenges to achieving a stable balance between supply and demand [7]. Thermal energy storage (TES) technologies are considered a promising solution to addressing the imbalance between thermal supply and heating

demand [8]. TES can store excess thermal energy generated during production phases and release it when needed. This technology is categorized into sensible heat storage [9], latent heat storage [10], and thermochemical energy storage (TCES) [11]. Particularly, TCES technology stands out due to its superior energy storage density ($\text{ESD} > 270 \text{ kWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), making it highly attractive for integration into solar systems and offering nearly twice the energy storage density compared to the first two types [12–14]. Furthermore, TCES systems convert thermal energy into chemical potential energy during the charging process, enabling minimal heat losses during storage [15].

Salt hydrates, such as $\text{CaCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [16], $\text{MgCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [17], $\text{SrBr}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [18] and $\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [19] are commonly used as thermochemical materials (TCMs) due to their high ESD [20], low cost [21], and non-toxicity [22]. Additionally, the regeneration temperatures of some salt hydrates are typically below $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, making them especially suitable for storing low-grade thermal energy, such as heat generated by solar power [23]. These characteristics make salt hydrates one of the

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most commonly used TCMs in current research on solar-driven low-temperature TCES systems. The operating principle of the salt hydrate-based low-temperature TCES systems is illustrated in Fig. 1 and described by Equation (1) [24]. During the charging process, high-temperature heat fluid from the heat source (i.e., solar thermal collector) heats the salt hydrate (i.e., $\text{Salt} \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$), causing the molecular bonds between the water molecules and the salt hydrate to break, resulting in dehydrated salt and water vapor. In this process, thermal energy is absorbed and converted into chemical potential energy for storage. Conversely, during the discharging process, when the dehydrated salt is exposed to water vapor or moist air, the salt recombines with water molecules, forming new chemical bonds and releasing heat in the process.

The deliquescence relative humidity of pure salts is characteristically low, which frequently leads to deliquescence during the discharging process of TCES systems. This phenomenon often results in agglomeration and subsequent energy losses [12]. Additionally, due to the sub-optimal mass transfer characteristics of salt hydrates, excessive accumulation in the reaction bed can cause uneven reaction kinetics, further contributing to deliquescence [25,26]. Not only does deliquescence diminish heat discharge efficiency, but it also precipitates corrosion, thereby compromising the structural integrity of the system components [21]. To address these challenges, one viable solution is the incorporation of salt hydrates into a porous matrix (e.g., expanded vermiculite [27], expanded perlite [21], expanded graphite [28], jute [29], silica gel [30–32] and metal-organic frameworks [33]), forming TCES composite materials. The structure of the porous substrates effectively enhances gas diffusion and mass transfer, mitigating uneven reaction kinetics and agglomeration during the discharging process, thereby improving the TCES system's thermal efficiency and cyclic stability [34]. However, since the substrates typically do not participate in the adsorption and desorption processes, the ESD of the composites is generally lower than that of pure salt hydrates [35].

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the reaction process of salt hydrates for solar heat storage in buildings.

Alternatively, optimizing the structural design of reactors also offers potential solutions to the issue of uneven reactions. Multilayer structure designs, in particular, show promise. Unlike packed bed reactors with haphazardly stacked TCMs, multilayer reactors consist of multiple packed bed units that process the incoming airflow nearly simultaneously. This design improves internal mass transfer capabilities, preventing excessive hydration of salt hydrates caused by uneven reactions [26]. It also increases the contact area between the TCMs and the airflow, reducing the flow rate through each reaction bed unit and decreasing the pressure drop across the reactor's inlet and outlet [8,36]. Additionally, other design optimizations, such as incorporating air diffusers [37], moving beds [38] and fluidized beds [39], have also been proposed to enhance the performance of TCES systems.

TCES systems can be categorized into two main types: open and closed systems [40]. In open systems, wet air serves as both a reactant and a heat transfer medium. During the discharging process, TCMs absorb water molecules from the moist air while simultaneously releasing heat to the air for space heating. Conversely, during the charging process, TCMs dehydrate and absorb heat as high-temperature air enters the reactor [41]. These characteristics make open TCES systems advantageous, as they eliminate the need for additional internal components [14], offering benefits in terms of structural simplicity, volumetric energy storage density, cost, and thermal efficiency [42–44]. However, central heating systems with hydronic (hot water) dominate residential space heating in regions such as the United Kingdom [45]. While using air as the heat transfer medium for space heating is both efficient and rapid, it poses significant challenges for integrating open TCES systems with existing hydronic central heating systems. Direct implementation of an open TCES system would require extensive air duct installations within buildings, which is particularly challenging in retrofitting older structures.

Due to the characteristics of closed systems, the heat released by the TCMs hydration can be directly transferred to the water flow through a heat exchanger during the discharging process. This facilitates easier integration of TCES systems into domestic hydronic central heating systems. However, closed TCES systems require reactors with high vacuum integrity and sealing. Additionally, they necessitate the use of evaporators and condensers to generate and collect water vapor [46]. This not only consumes significant energy to maintain the vacuum state but also results in complex system structures and high costs, making large-scale commercial applications more challenging [14,26].

To address these challenges, previous research introduced two types of open water-based TCES systems: an open TCES system incorporating a detached finned microchannel flat-tube heat exchanger (i.e., DFHEX-TCES) and an open TCES system integrating an internal bare microchannel flat-tube heat exchanger (i.e., IBHEX-TCES), their schematics are shown in Fig. 2. Both systems can be seamlessly integrated into domestic central heating systems without the high construction costs and energy demands associated with maintaining a vacuum in closed TCES systems. These open water-based TCES systems have been demonstrated to be viable through prior simulation studies. To experimentally assess and compare the thermal performance of the DFHEX-TCES and IBHEX-TCES configurations, a versatile TCES experimental setup is constructed in a laboratory setting at the University of Nottingham, UK. Two commercially available heat exchangers (shown in Fig. 3), featuring different designs and installation configurations, are integrated with this TCES system to test and compare the performance of the DFHEX-TCES and IBHEX-TCES schemes in single-layer TCES reactors under various operating conditions. Subsequently, the cyclic performance of the single-layer and multilayer DFHEX-TCES systems is investigated. This study contributes valuable experimental evidence to the growing body of research on TCES systems, demonstrating the feasibility of DFHEX-TCES configuration for large-scale applications.

Fig. 2. 3D Diagrams of the TCES reaction bed with embedded IBHEX unit in the IBHEX-TCES reactor (left); the TCES reaction bed and DFHEX in DFHEX-TCES reactor (right) [47,48].

2. TCM selection and synthesis

In this study, a TCM composite was synthesized by using expanded vermiculite as the host material and impregnating it with CaCl_2 . CaCl_2 is widely favored in low-temperature TCES research, either as a pure salt TCM or as a raw material of the TCM composite materials, due to several key factors. First, CaCl_2 is readily available and cost-effective, with industrial-grade and laboratory-grade prices ranging from 0.1 to 0.2 £/kg [49] and 50–100 £/kg [50], respectively. Second, it has strong water uptake capacity and high ESD, offering superior performance compared to many other salt hydrates [27]. Third, CaCl_2 demonstrates high chemical stability and non-toxic properties, making it safer and more durable than many other salts [51]. Lastly, its regeneration temperature is relatively low (i.e., below 100 °C), making it particularly suitable for low-temperature TCES applications [51]. These characteristics position CaCl_2 as a highly promising salt hydrate for domestic low-temperature TCES systems. The reversible thermochemical reaction of CaCl_2 is represented in Equation (2).

Expanded vermiculite is a porous matrix formed from raw vermiculite through high-temperature treatment, characterized by its lightweight, non-toxic, and chemically inert properties. These characteristics make expanded vermiculite an ideal matrix for the preparation of TCM composites [52]. TCM composites composed of vermiculite and CaCl_2 exhibit excellent water uptake and ESD, outperforming many other commonly used TCM composite materials, and show significant potential for application in open TCES systems [53]. In this study, the composite materials were prepared using the conventional single impregnation method. The expanded vermiculite was first dried in an oven at 150 °C for 24 h to ensure complete desiccation, followed by cooling to room temperature. Subsequently, the fully dried vermiculite was placed into a container and submerged entirely in a saturated CaCl_2 solution for 1 h. After immersion, the composite material was transferred to a filter to remove excess solution and then dried in the oven at

Fig. 3. Photos of (a) the bare microchannel flat tube heat exchanger (used as an IBHEX); and (b) the finned microchannel flat tube heat exchanger (used as a DFHEX).

150 °C for an additional 24 h to achieve complete dehydration. Expanded vermiculite was supplied by Fisher Scientific UK Ltd., and the anhydrous CaCl_2 was sourced from Merck Life Science UK Ltd. Fig. 4 presents photos and scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of both the expanded vermiculite and the synthesized TCM composite material (i.e., vermiculite- CaCl_2). Detailed characterization information for the synthesized composite is available in Table 1.

3. Experimental setup description

A versatile TCES experimental setup was constructed in the laboratory, and a photo and a schematic diagram are shown in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively. This system setup mainly consists of a spray humidifier, a water-to-air heat exchanger, an axial duct fan, an inline duct electric heater, a TCES reactor, and an external heat recovery unit (HRU). The

Fig. 4. Photos and SEM images of the raw expanded vermiculite and vermiculite- CaCl_2 composite.

Table 1

Physical properties of vermiculite-CaCl₂ composites synthesized by conventional single impregnation.

	Characterization methods	Vermiculite-CaCl ₂ composite material (conventional single impregnation method)
Volumetric ESD (kWh/m ³)	Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)	230
Porosity (%)	Mercury Intrusion Porosimetry (MIP)	73
Apparent density (g/cm ³)	Mercury Intrusion Porosimetry (MIP)	0.49
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Mercury Intrusion Porosimetry (MIP)	1.75
CaCl ₂ content (%)	Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES)	52
Water uptake (g/g)	Constant temperature and humidity	0.68

specifications of these key system components are listed in Table 2. K-type thermocouples were utilized to measure the inlet and outlet water temperatures, as well as the average temperature of the air after passing through the reaction bed. Humidity and temperature sensors were placed in the inlet and outlet ducts of each component to monitor changes in air humidity and temperature as the air passed through each stage of the system. Additionally, an airflow meter was installed behind the reactor outlet, preceded by a sufficient length of straight duct to ensure the air entered the flow meter in a stable state. The models, measurement ranges, and accuracies of the aforementioned sensors are detailed in Table 3.

The versatile experimental setup enables investigations of the proposed water-based TCES systems in various configurations, including single-layer and multilayer reactors, as well as systems incorporating IBHEX and DFHEX. The reaction bed unit in the TCES reactor measures 340 mm × 340 mm × 60 mm (L × W × H) and is filled with the vermiculite-CaCl₂ composite material. Two different type heat exchangers used for integration in the TCES system to form the water-based system are shown in Fig. 3: internal bare microchannel flat-tube heat exchanger (IBHEX, X001-SAH264) and detached finned microchannel flat-tube heat exchanger (DFHEX, SD10-5). Both were sourced from Sanhua Holding Group Co., Ltd. Their dimensions are 290 mm × 290 mm × 20 mm and 330 mm × 284 mm × 16 mm (L × W × H),

respectively.

A 3D view of the water-based TCES system and its workflow during both the discharging and charging processes is shown in Fig. 7. During the discharging process, external air firstly is humidified by the spray humidifier, which is equipped with a honeycomb cooling pad. By spraying a large volume of constant-temperature water onto the pad, the wet-bulb temperature of the airflow passing through the honeycomb cooling pad closely approaches the temperature of the sprayed water. This enables precise regulation of the absolute humidity of the humidified airflow by controlling the temperature of the sprayed water. The humidified airflow then passes through the water-to-air heat exchanger, where its temperature is adjusted to the desired inlet temperature by constant temperature water supplied from a boiler or water tank. This ensures the airflow reaches the predefined temperature and absolute humidity (or relative humidity). The processed airflow then enters the HRU, where it is preheated by the hot air exiting the TCES reactor. After being preheated, the airflow moves through the duct into the TCES reactor. In the reactor, CaCl₂ absorbs moisture from the airflow and releases heat through the hydration reaction, thereby heating both the passing reactor airflow and water. This heated water is subsequently conveyed to the building's central heating system. The remaining heat exits the reactor with the airflow; a portion of this residual heat is recovered by the HRU, while the remainder is released into the surrounding environment.

During the charging process, the electric heater simulates the low-temperature heat source required for the TCES system. The processed and preheated airflow is further heated by the electric heater before entering the reactor. In the reactor, a portion of the heat from the hot air flow is transferred to the TCM composite material, inducing its dehydration. The remaining waste heat exits the reactor with the airflow, part of this waste heat is utilized by the heat exchanger to preheat the incoming air, while the rest is discharged into the environment.

In the experiments for water based TCES reactors, the inlet temperature for the HEX was set at 27 °C, which is a typical return water temperature for residential underfloor heating systems. The same temperature was also applied at the reactor inlet. To ensure that the pressure drop within the reactor remained within the static pressure range provided by conventional commercial fans, the benchmark air flow rate was set at approximately 17 m³ h⁻¹ (frontal velocity of reactor bed is 0.04 m s⁻¹), with a water flow rate through the HEX set at 9 L h⁻¹. The initial phase of the experiments assessed the performance of two water-based thermochemical energy storage (TCES) reactors under conditions of low (8 g kg⁻¹) and high (10 g kg⁻¹) absolute humidity at the inlet air.

Fig. 5. A photo of the versatile TCES test rig.

Note: The red dot ● represents the relative humidity & temperature sensor (RH&T sensor) and thermocouple

Fig. 6. Schematic of the versatile TCES experimental setup.

Table 2
Specifications of the key system components.

Device	Manufacturer	Model	Specification
Electric duct heater	Omega	AHF-12240	Heater Power: 2 kW
Water pump	Kamoer	KK1800	Pump type: Peristaltic Pump Flow range: 0.03–1500 ml/min
Heat recovery unit	UK Exchangers	HO200/2.1/C-250	Dimensions: 200 × 250 × 283 (mm) Nominal plate distance: 2.1 mm
Water bath	Nickel-Electro	NE4-14P	Temperature Range: Ambient +5 °C–99 °C Heater Power: 1.25 kW Chamber Capacity: 14 L
DFHEX	Sanhua	SD-10	340 mm × 340 mm × 16 mm (L × W × H) 23 fins per inch
IBHEX	Sanhua	X001-SAH264	290 mm × 290 mm × 16 mm (L × W × H) Finless
Inline duct fan	SENSDAR	SE-A100	Air Flow Rate: 275 m ³ /h Air Pressure: 334 Pa

Subsequently, the reactors were tested under conditions of low (17 m³ h⁻¹) and high (34 m³ h⁻¹) air flow rates. Throughout the comprehensive system testing, the inlet temperature was set closer to the typical indoor winter conditions at 22 °C. Both individual reactors and the entire system were evaluated under the realistic condition, followed by multiple charge/discharge cycles to assess the system robustness. Additionally, comparative tests were conducted between multilayer and single-layer designs under identical experimental conditions, with repeated trials

Table 3
Specifications of measurement instruments.

Devices	Manufacturer/Model	Measurement Range	Accuracy
Humidity-temperature sensor	Sensirion, SHT45	–40–125 °C 0–100 % RH	±0.1 °C ±1 %
K-type thermocouple	Electrotherm, 282 RS	0–1000 °C	±0.75 %
Air flow meter	Sensing Precision, Flowgrid	0–60 m/s	±1 %
Data Logger	Pico, TC-08	–270–1820 °C	±0.025 °C

performed on the multilayer configurations.

4. Performance evaluation metrics and uncertainty analysis

4.1. Performance evaluation metrics

The peak water temperature lift and the duration of temperature maintenance in the water-based TCES system are determined through direct measurements. However, the heat absorbed by the TCMs during the charging process, the heat released by the TCMs during the discharging process, and the heat absorbed by the water flow need to be calculated based on measured data.

The heat absorbed by the TCMs during the charging process can be calculated by:

$$Q_{\text{TCM,ab}} = \int \dot{V}_a \rho_a C_a (T_{r,\text{in}} - T_{\text{HEX,in}}) dt \quad (3)$$

where, $Q_{\text{TCM,ab}}$ is the heat absorbed by the TCMs in the charging process, kJ; \dot{V}_a is the volume flow rate of air, m³•s⁻¹; ρ_a and C_a are the density

Fig. 7. 3D view of the proposed TCES system and its workflow during the discharging and charging processes.

and specific heat capacity of air, $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and $\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, respectively; $T_{r,\text{in}}$ is the reactor inlet temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$; and $T_{\text{HEX},\text{in}}$ is the temperature of the air entering the heat exchanger after passing through the reaction bed, $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The heat released by the TCMs during the discharging process can be calculated by:

$$Q_{\text{TCM, re}} = \int \dot{V}_a \rho_a C_a (T_{\text{HEX},\text{in}} - T_{r,\text{in}}) dt \quad (4)$$

The heat absorbed by the water during the discharging process can be calculated by:

$$Q_{w,\text{ab}} = \int \dot{V}_w \rho_w C_w (T_{w,\text{out}} - T_{w,\text{in}}) dt \quad (5)$$

where, $Q_{w,\text{ab}}$ is the heat absorbed by the water in the discharging process, kJ; \dot{V}_w is the volume flow rate of water, $\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$; ρ_w and C_w are the density and specific heat capacity of water, $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and $\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, respectively; $T_{w,\text{in}}$ and $T_{w,\text{out}}$ are the inlet and outlet temperatures of water, $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively.

4.2. Uncertainty analysis

The combined standard uncertainty at each measurement point is classified into Type A and Type B. Type A uncertainty is quantified through statistical methods, involving indicators like standard deviation or variance from repeated measurements. Type B uncertainty is derived from non-statistical information sources. The overall uncertainty can be expressed by the following equation:

$$u = \sqrt{u_A^2 + u_{B1}^2 + u_{B2}^2 + \dots + u_{Bn}^2} \quad (6)$$

where u_A is Type A uncertainty, and u_B is Type B uncertainty.

Type A uncertainty can be calculated by:

$$u_A = \frac{s}{n} \quad (7)$$

where s is the standard deviation, and n is the number of measurements.

Type B uncertainty is used to quantify the measurement uncertainty introduced by equipment specifications, calibration certificates, or other non-experimental sources, and its core equation is as follows:

$$u_B = \frac{\text{Sensor accuracy}}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (8)$$

when calculating Type B uncertainty, it is assumed that the sensor error is uniformly distributed (rectangular distribution) within its given maximum error range. The rectangular distribution assumes that each error value within that range has an equal probability of occurring. In the equation, $\sqrt{3}$ is derived from the statistical properties of the rectangular distribution as the distribution factor.

The uncertainty of the heat absorbed by the TCM during the charging process, the heat released by the TCM during the discharging process, and the heat absorbed by the water flow are determined using the Gaussian propagation of uncertainty rule [36]. The uncertainty of the heat absorbed by the TCM during the charging process is calculated using the following formula:

$$u(Q_{\text{TCM,ab}}) = \sqrt{\left[\frac{\partial Q_{\text{TCM,ab}}}{\partial \dot{V}_a} u(\dot{V}_a) \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\partial Q_{\text{TCM,ab}}}{\partial \Delta T} u(\Delta T) \right]^2} \quad (9)$$

where, ΔT is the difference between $T_{r,\text{in}}$ and $T_{\text{HEX},\text{in}}$, $^{\circ}\text{C}$; it can be described by:

$$u(\Delta T) = \sqrt{u(T_{r,\text{in}})^2 + u(T_{\text{HEX},\text{in}})^2} \quad (10)$$

Since the sensors required for calculating the heat released by the TCM during the discharging process and for calculating the heat absorbed by the TCM during the charging process are the same, their uncertainties are identical. The uncertainty of the heat transferred to the water during the discharging phase can be calculated using the following equation:

$$u(Q_{w,\text{ab}}) = \sqrt{\left[\frac{\partial Q_{w,\text{ab}}}{\partial \dot{V}_w} u(\dot{V}_w) \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\partial Q_{w,\text{ab}}}{\partial \Delta T} u(\Delta T) \right]^2} \quad (11)$$

where, ΔT is the difference between $T_{w,\text{out}}$ and $T_{w,\text{in}}$, $^{\circ}\text{C}$; it can be described by:

$$u(\Delta T) = \sqrt{u(T_{w,\text{in}})^2 + u(T_{w,\text{out}})^2} \quad (12)$$

The uncertainty of the heat absorbed by the TCM during the charging process, the heat released by the TCM during the discharging process, and the heat absorbed by the water flow was computed using the above

equations. The results are 1.38 %, 1.03 %, and 2.12 %, respectively.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Single-layer water-based TCES system

Experiments are conducted to compare the performance of the water-based TCES system with an internal bare microchannel tube heat exchanger (i.e., IBHEX-TCES system) with that of the TCES system employing a detached finned heat exchanger DFHEX (i.e., DFHEX-TCES). Fig. 8 illustrates the internal structures and the airflow paths within both single-layer water-based TCES reactors. To assess the impact of heat exchanger selection on the performance of water-based TCES systems, in this experiment, the heat recovery unit was not included; therefore, the warm exhaust expelled by the reactor was directly vented outdoors and did not contribute to the preheating of incoming air. The temperatures of both the inlet air and water were set at 27 °C throughout the experiments.

5.1.1. Reactor performance comparison between two configurations under different absolute humidity conditions

The single-layer IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES reactors were tested under conditions of both high and low inlet absolute humidity. During testing, the airflow through the reactor and the water flow through the HEX were maintained at approximately 17 m³ h⁻¹ (corresponding to a frontal airflow velocity of 0.04 m s⁻¹ across the reactor bed) and 9 L h⁻¹, respectively. Fig. 9 presents the discharging performance for the single-layer DFHEX-TCES under inlet absolute humidities of 8 g kg⁻¹ and 10 g kg⁻¹. With an inlet absolute humidity of 8 g kg⁻¹, the temperature of the airflow entering the heat exchanger after the reaction bed ($T_{\text{HEX,in}}$) rapidly increased, peaking at 41.44 °C within approximately 15 min. As heat transferred from the air to the water in the DFHEX, the outlet water temperature ($T_{\text{w,out}}$) also rose, reaching a peak of 32.81 °C with a temperature lift of 5.72 °C. During this discharging process, the water temperature lift remained above 5 °C for 32 min, while lifts above 4 °C and 3 °C were maintained for 82 and 142 min, respectively. During this period, the TCM composite material within the single-layer DFHEX-TCES absorbed 280 g of water molecules from the air, releasing 735 kJ of thermal energy, with 65 % of the generated heat successfully transferred to the water.

When the inlet absolute humidity was raised to 10 g kg⁻¹, both $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and $T_{\text{w,out}}$ reached their peak temperatures more quickly and at higher levels than under the 8 g kg⁻¹ condition. Specifically, $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and $T_{\text{w,out}}$ peaked at 46.34 °C and 34.27 °C, respectively. This rise in peak values was attributed to the higher partial pressure of water vapor, which enhanced the kinetic driving force of the CaCl₂ hydration reaction within the TCM composite material, accelerating the reaction rate. The faster and more vigorous hydration reaction allowed $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and $T_{\text{w,out}}$ to reach higher peaks more rapidly, as more water molecules participated in the reaction, releasing more heat. Fig. 9 also shows the difference in absolute humidity between the inlet and outlet of the reactor under varying conditions, reflecting the quantity of water molecules absorbed during the discharging process. With an inlet absolute humidity of 10 g kg⁻¹, the duration for which the water temperature rise in the heat exchanger stayed above 5 °C, 4 °C, and 3 °C extended to 70, 120, and 205 min, respectively. This prolonged temperature rise resulted from the increased hydration reaction of TCM composite due to the higher absolute humidity.

The discharging performance of the single-layer IBHEX-TCES under two inlet absolute humidity conditions is presented in Fig. 10. An increase in inlet humidity also enhanced both the peak temperature lift and the duration of the temperature lift in the water flow of the single-layer IBHEX-TCES. At absolute humidity levels of 8 g kg⁻¹ and 10 g kg⁻¹, the water flow peak temperature lift reached 5.67 °C and 7.35 °C, respectively, comparable to the performance of the single-layer DFHEX-TCES. However, the single-layer IBHEX-TCES exhibited a significant disadvantage in terms of the duration of the water temperature lift. The duration in which the water flow temperature lift remained above 5 °C in the single-layer IBHEX-TCES was at least 15 min shorter than that in the DFHEX-TCES under both humidity conditions. This performance gap is primarily due to the space occupied by the IBHEX, which reduces the capacity of the TCMS within the reactor.

The overall performance of the two water-based TCES reactors under high and low absolute humidity conditions is presented in Table 4. The single-layer IBHEX-TCES achieved slightly higher heat release than the single-layer DFHEX-TCES, despite containing a lower mass of TCM composite material. During the testing period, the heat released by the TCM composite in the IBHEX-TCES was 752 kJ and 996 kJ at inlet absolute humidities of 8 g kg⁻¹ and 10 g kg⁻¹, respectively. The slightly higher heat release observed in the IBHEX-TCES configuration can be

Fig. 8. Reactor internal structures and airflow pathways of two single-layer water-based TCES reactors.

Air flow rate: $17 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ (reaction bed frontal velocity: $0.04 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)

Fig. 9. Temperature and absolute humidity measurements at various points in the single-layer DFHEX-TCES reactor under high and low absolute humidity conditions.

attributed to the embedded structure of the IBHEX. The integration of water channels within the composite material increases the overall porosity of the reactor bed. Although this reduces the mass of TCMS, it significantly enhances the contact surface area with the humid air, thereby improving mass transfer efficiency within the bed. These accelerate the hydration rate of CaCl_2 in the composite material, enabling more heat to be released simultaneously. Moreover, the embedded structure of the IBHEX shortens the heat transfer path and reduces thermal resistance, thereby facilitating more rapid heat transfer. During portions of the discharging process, this faster heat release compensates for the overall TCM composite mass, resulting in similar peak outlet water temperatures between the single-layer IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES.

The single-layer IBHEX-TCES contains 20 %–30 % less TCM composite material by weight in a reaction bed of the same dimensions. This reduction results from the IBHEX occupying space otherwise available for TCM composite material. Although the IBHEX employs a bare microchannel water channel design, the dense arrangement of the water channels combined with the large particle size of the existing TCM composite (3–8 mm) leads to lower space utilization between water channels than simulated. This configuration increases the porosity of the reaction bed, facilitating the hydration reaction and heat release of CaCl_2 , which compensates for the reduced composite mass in the initial phases of operation. However, the reduced TCM composite mass ultimately limits the total heat released over the full process duration.

The results indicate that the single-layer water-based TCES reactors

achieve greater peak water temperature lift, longer durations of temperature lift, and increased TCM heat release and transfer to water under a high inlet absolute humidity condition (10 g kg^{-1}) compared to lower humidity (8 g kg^{-1}). However, elevated inlet humidity also results in extensive deliquescence within the reaction bed, which not only affects the system's cyclic capability but may also pose a risk of corrosion, potentially compromising the structural integrity of the reactor. Additionally, achieving an inlet absolute humidity of 10 g kg^{-1} is more challenging and more demanding, as it requires supplementary humidification. In contrast, an absolute humidity of 8 g kg^{-1} is often typical of indoor air in winter and can be supplied directly to the system without additional equipment.

5.1.2. Reactor performance comparison between two configurations under different airflow volumetric flow rates

The discharging performance of two single-layer water-based TCES reactors is compared under conditions of high and low air flow rates, with the water flow through the heat exchanger remaining constant at 9 L h^{-1} . The absolute humidity of the air entering the reactor was set at 8 g kg^{-1} . The discharging performance of both single-layer TCES reactors at a low air flow rate ($17 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$) is shown in Figs. 9 and 10, while their performance at a high air flow rates ($34 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$) is presented in Fig. 11. As the air flow rate increases from low to high, the peak $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ of the single-layer DFHEX-TCES and the peak water temperature lift in both reactors increase. Specifically, when the air flow rate increases from $17 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ to $34 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$, the peak $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and water temperature lift in the

Air flow rate: 17 m³·h⁻¹ (reaction bed frontal velocity: 0.04 m·s⁻¹)

Fig. 10. Temperature and absolute humidity measurements at various points in the single-layer IBHEX-TCES reactor under high and low absolute humidity conditions.

Table 4

Overall data of these two single-layer water-based TCES reactors under high and low absolute humidity conditions.

	Single-layer DFHEX-TCES		Single-layer IBHEX-TCES	
	8 g kg ⁻¹	10 g kg ⁻¹	8 g kg ⁻¹	10 g kg ⁻¹
Start mass (g)	1557	1527	1091	1270
Increased weight (g)	280	350	281	367
Heat released from TCMS (kJ)	735	962	752	996
Heat absorbed by water (kJ)	493	623	416	561
Effectiveness of HEX (%)	67	65	55	56

single-layer DFHEX-TCES increase to 44.77 °C and 8.85 °C, respectively, representing an increase of over 3 °C compared to the lower air flow rate condition. Similarly, the peak water temperature lift in the single-layer IBHEX-TCES increases by nearly 30 %. This increase is attributed to the higher air flow rate, which supplies more water molecules to the CaCl₂ in the TCM composite material, enabling more CaCl₂ to participate in the hydration reaction and release additional heat. While higher air velocities reduce the time the air spends in the reaction bed, the increased availability of water molecules for the hydration reaction has a greater effect on temperature than the reduced heating time within this range.

As the air flow rate in both single-layer water-based TCES reactors increases from low to high, the duration for which the water

temperature lifts remain above 5 °C also increases. At an air flow rate of 34 m³ h⁻¹, the duration for which the water temperature lift remains above 5 °C in the single-layer DFHEX-TCES and IBHEX-TCES is 90 min and 29 min, respectively, nearly tripling and doubling compared to the lower air flow conditions. This increase is due to the higher air flow rate, which allows more CaCl₂ to hydrate with water molecules early in the process, resulting in a more concentrated heat release during the initial stages. Moreover, both the heat release rate of the TCM composite material and the heating power of the reactor increase with the air flow rate. These changes in power dynamics during the discharging process are displayed in Fig. 11. The increased air flow rate improves the heat transfer efficiency between the air and the TCM composite material, leading to more heat being transferred to both the air and water.

From the above analysis, it is evident that both single-layer water-based TCES reactors perform better under high air flow rate conditions. However, further increasing the air flow rate may result in an excessive pressure drop between the inlet and outlet of the reactor, making it challenging to select a fan capable of handling both the required air flow rate and the resulting pressure difference. Additionally, the higher pressure drop leads to increased power consumption. Under the high air flow rate condition, the single-layer DFHEX-TCES outperforms the single-layer IBHEX-TCE, both in terms of the load of TCM and the water temperature lift. Furthermore, the internal structure of the single-layer IBHEX-TCES reactor is more complex. The embedded structure exposes the IBHEX directly to the TCM composite material, which can potentially lead to corrosion of the IBHEX, and also complicates the

Absolute humidity: 8 g·kg⁻¹

Fig. 11. Dynamic temperature of two single-layer water-based TCES reactors under high airflow conditions; and comparison of TCM heat release power and water heating power of two single-layer water-based TCES reactors under high and low airflow rates.

filling or replacement of the TCM composite. Experimental testing indicates that the time required to fill or replace material in the single-layer IBHEX-TCES is approximately five times longer than that in the single-layer DFHEX-TCES.

5.1.3. Cyclic performance of the complete single-layer water-based DFHEX-TCES system

Given the superior performance of the single-layer DFHEX reactor, comprehensive testing of the single-layer DFHEX-TCES system was

Fig. 12. Temperature variation at various measurement points during the discharging process in the single-layer DFHEX-TCES system with and without HRU.

conducted under conditions closely simulating real-world applications. Air and water inlet temperatures were set at 22 °C and 27 °C, respectively, with an inlet absolute humidity of 8 g kg⁻¹ (corresponding to a relative humidity of about 50 %). To evaluate the system's stability and reliability, four consecutive charging/discharging cycle tests were performed, providing insights into the system's performance under consistent operating conditions.

Tests were carried out to investigate the impact of the HRU on the discharging performance of the single-layer DFHEX TCES. For this discharging testing, the TCM composite materials were dried at 150 °C for 24 h to ensure a fully dehydrated starting state. The dynamic temperature profiles recorded at various measurement points are displayed in Fig. 12, with the system incorporating the HRU shown on the right and the configuration without the HRU shown on the left. Under more realistic conditions, the single-layer DFHEX-TCES system without an HRU exhibited reduced peak $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and water temperature lift compared to the idealized testing conditions described in the previous section, with values of 39.84 °C and 6.17 °C, respectively. The water temperature lift decreased by over 30 %. The duration for which the water temperature lift remained above 5 °C and 4 °C also decreased to approximately one-third of the previous duration. This reduction is primarily attributed to lower inlet temperatures under realistic conditions, where a considerable portion of the heat released by the TCM composite was directed toward compensating for the temperature gap between the cooler incoming air and water flow. In contrast, the complete single-layer DFHEX-TCES system with an HRU demonstrated notable improvements, achieving a peak $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ of 40.26 °C and a water temperature lift of 6.82 °C. Additionally, the duration of the water temperature lift increased significantly, with the time above 5 °C nearly doubling. This enhancement is due to the HRU's ability to recover waste heat from the reactor outlet and transfer it to the incoming air, effectively preheating it and boosting overall system efficiency.

Following the full-system discharging tests that used fully dried TCM composite material, four consecutive charging and discharging cycles were performed under conditions that closely resembled real-world

scenarios. During the charging process, an electric heater simulated a low-temperature heat source by raising the system temperature to 90 °C, while it remained inactive during the discharging process. The temperature variations at various measurement points across these cycles are displayed in Fig. 13. As seen, the data indicate relatively consistent temperature profiles across all cycles, with no notable changes in dynamic temperatures as the cycle count increased, highlighting the system's stability and repeatability under these conditions. At the beginning of the charging process, a substantial temperature difference between the reactor inlet and outlet was observed, resulting from the rapid dehydration and heat absorption by the salt hydrates in the TCM composite material. During the initial period, both $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and the reactor outlet temperature rose quickly, then gradually slowed in their increase and finally approaching the inlet temperature of 90 °C by around the fifth hour, indicating the near-completion of the reaction. As shown in Fig. 13, the incorporation of the HRU enabled a reduction of over 40 % in heat consumption during the charging process. The DFHEX added minimal thermal energy consumption during the charging stage, as the temperature difference between $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and the reactor outlet remained negligible throughout all four charging cycles.

During the discharging process, air preheated by the HRU reached approximately 27 °C within 30 min before gradually declining. Compared to the testing conducted with fully dried TCM composite material, the peak water temperature lift in the cyclic testing decreased by approximately 2.5 °C, and the heat absorbed by the water over a 210-min period dropped by 24 %. This reduction occurred because the inlet temperature of 90 °C was insufficient to fully dry the TCM composite material (i.e., salt hydrate in TCES composite material converting completely to anhydrous salt where the conversion degree, $\alpha = 1$). Over successive cycles, slight decreases were noted in the mass changes during the charging/discharging processes, the heat absorbed by the TCM composite during charging, and the heat absorbed by the water flow, as summarized in Table 5. These declines were due to minor clumping within the TCM composite material resulting from deliquescence, which

Fig. 13. Temperature variations at various measurement points within the single-layer DFHEX-TCES system during four successive cycle tests.

partially restricted the dehydration/hydration reactions of CaCl_2 as the cycles progressed.

5.2. Multilayer DFHEX-TCES system

While the single-layer water-based TCES system demonstrates good performance in terms of peak water temperature lift, its ability to sustain this lift over time remains limited. In testing the reactor and the complete system, the duration of water temperature lift remained above 5°C was 90 min and 65 min, respectively. This limitation is largely due to the 6 cm thickness of the reaction bed in the single-layer water-based TCES system, which restricts the amount of TCM composite material that can be incorporated. Additionally, the TCM's low permeability and limited thermal conductivity present operational challenges, particularly when considering scale-up. Increasing the reaction bed thickness could exacerbate issues, leading to uneven reaction distribution, excessive salt hydration, and degradation of thermal performance. Moreover, a thicker bed results in higher pressure drops across the reactor, increasing both energy consumption and overall system costs.

A multilayer TCES reactor, comprising parallel packed bed units, maybe a better choice for large-scale applications. This configuration enhances contact between the TCM and airflow, thereby improving heat and mass transfer while minimizing internal pressure drops, collectively boosting system performance. Additionally, the multilayer design ensures a more uniform airflow distribution within the reaction bed, alleviating issues of excessive salt hydration. A laboratory-scale multilayer water-based TCES system was constructed and evaluated, with its internal structure displayed in Fig. 14. In this multilayer setup, gaps between four horizontally placed reaction beds create three inlet channels and two exhaust channels, each 20 mm in height. The exhaust channel sides near the reactor's inlet are sealed to direct the airflow effectively. Upon entering the reactor, airflow is funnelled into the inlet channels, where the closed ends drive the flow up or down through the reaction beds before passing through the DFHEX into the exhaust channels.

Previous tests with the single-layer IBHEX-TCES structure revealed notable limitations with respect to TCM load capacity and the time-consuming filling and replacement processes. Incorporating IBHEX into the multilayer water-based TCES configuration introduces significant complexity to the internal reactor design. In addition, filling and replacing the TCM in multilayer IBHEX requires numerous disconnections and reconnections of the water flow pathways, leading to substantial time expenditure compared to the DFHEX setup, where the heat exchanger remains permanently installed at the reactor's outlet. These operations also expose dry TCM to ambient humidity, leading to undesired heat release. Consequently, this study excludes multilayer IBHEX-TCES from further comparison, focusing exclusively on the multilayer DFHEX-TCES configuration.

5.2.1. Multilayer DFHEX-TCES reactor performance under different air flow rates

The multilayer DFHEX-TCES reactor was tested under both low and

high air flow conditions, with the temperature variations at various measurement points shown in Fig. 15. For these experiments, no heat recovery unit was included, and exhaust gases were directly discharged outdoors without contributing to preheating the incoming air. The inlet air and water temperatures were set at 27°C .

At a low air flow rate of $17\text{ m}^3\text{ h}^{-1}$ (corresponding to a frontal air velocity of 0.01 m s^{-1} across the reactor bed), the peak $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and water temperature lift are 39.2°C and 5.33°C , respectively. This represents decreases of 2.24°C and 0.39°C compared to the single-layer configuration. The reduction is attributed to the lower average air flow velocity through the reactor beds, which slows down the hydration rate of CaCl_2 and overall heat release. However, the durations during which the water temperature lift exceeded 5°C and 4°C in the multilayer reactor were 66 min and 276 min, respectively, approximately twice and 3.5 times longer than those observed in the single-layer reactor. This prolonged duration is due to the higher TCM loading capacity in the multilayer reactor.

When the air flow rate increased to $34\text{ m}^3\text{ h}^{-1}$ (corresponding to a frontal air velocity of 0.02 m s^{-1} across the reactor bed), the multilayer reactor exhibited a slight increase in peak $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and a noticeable water temperature lift improvement of 0.17°C and 2.15°C , respectively. This enhancement results from the higher air flow rate, which supplies more water molecules per unit time, accelerating hydration of CaCl_2 and heat release. Additionally, the increased air flow rate enhances convective heat transfer between the air and water, thereby transferring more heat to the water within the same time frame. At an air flow rate of $34\text{ m}^3\text{ h}^{-1}$, the duration during which the water temperature lift exceeded 5°C is 220 min (3 h 40 min), which is 3.3 times longer than the duration at the low air flow condition and 2.4 times longer than that of the single-layer under the same air flow rate condition.

5.2.2. Cyclic performance of the complete multilayer water-based DFHEX-TCES system

To evaluate the feasibility of the complete multilayer water-based DFHEX-TCES system, testing was carried out under conditions that closely simulate real-world applications. Using fully dried TCM composite materials, the monitored dynamic temperature variations at different measurement points are displayed in Fig. 16. Air and water flow rates were set at $34\text{ m}^3\text{ h}^{-1}$ and 9 L h^{-1} , respectively.

The complete multilayer DFHEX-TCES system achieved a peak $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ of 37.9°C and a maximum water temperature lift of 5.91°C , showing reductions of 2.36°C and 0.91°C , respectively, compared to the single-layer system. However, the multilayer system demonstrated substantial improvements in the duration during which the water temperature lift remained above 5°C and 4°C for 146 min and 120 min, respectively, representing increases of 125 % and 195 %.

Both the reactor-level and complete system-level tests confirm that the multilayer DFHEX-TCES configuration significantly extends the duration of the water temperature lift above 5°C and 4°C . While there is a slight trade-off in peak water temperature lift, the configuration exhibits enhanced capability for sustained thermal output, making it better and efficient for applications requiring extended heat delivery.

Table 5

Overall performance data of the single-layer DFHEX-TCES system across four consecutive cycles.

Cycle No.	t (min)	m_i (g)	Δm (g)	α_i	α_f	Peak ΔT_w ($^\circ\text{C}$)	$Q_{\text{TCM,ab}}$ (kJ)	$Q_{\text{TCM,re}}$ (kJ)	$Q_{w,ab}$ (kJ)	HRU Recovery efficiency (%)
Discharging (From the fully dried)	210	1543	413	1	0.46	6.82		1104	550	
Discharging (From the fully dried)	300	1543	550	1	0.28	6.82		1454	692	57
Cycle 1: charging	300	2093	393	0.28	0.79		1358			62
Cycle 1: discharging	210	1700	399	0.79	0.27	4.32		1075	417	57
Cycle 2: charging	300	2099	390	0.27	0.78		1348			62
Cycle 2: discharging	210	1709	399	0.78	0.26	4.23		1035	402	57
Cycle 3: charging	300	2108	388	0.26	0.77		1299			62
Cycle 3: discharging	210	1720	397	0.77	0.25	4.21		1020	387	57
Cycle 4: charging	300	2117	385	0.25	0.75		1247			62
Cycle 4: discharging	210	1732	395	0.75	0.24	4.13		1008	382	57

Fig. 14. Photo and illustration of internal structure and airflow pathways of the multilayer water-based TCES reactor.

Absolute humidity: 8 g·kg⁻¹

Fig. 15. Temperature profiles at various points in the multilayer DFHEX-TCES under low and high air flow rates.

Following the complete discharge test of the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system using fully dried TCM composite material, four cycles of charging and discharging were conducted to further assess the system's cyclic performance under conditions resembling practical applications. Similar setups were employed as described in the testing for the single-layer system. Fig. 17 illustrates the dynamic temperature profiles at various measurement points across these cycles. In the first charging cycle, the reactor outlet temperature approached the inlet temperature only after 10 h, nearly twice the duration observed in the single-layer DFHEX-TCES system, due to the greater amount of TCM composite material in

the multilayer configuration. During discharging, the peak $T_{HEX,in}$ and water temperature lift in the multilayer system were 33.14 °C and 3.52 °C, respectively, reductions of 4.1 °C and 0.8 °C compared to the single-layer system. This reduction was attributed to the lower per-unit-area air velocity through the multilayer reaction bed equivalent air flow rates. Despite these reductions, the multilayer system demonstrated a longer temperature lift duration, maintaining a water temperature lift above 3 °C for about 5 h, approximately 1.5 times longer than the single-layer system.

To improve the water temperature lift to a more practically useable

Fig. 16. Dynamic temperature variations at various measurement points during discharging in the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system with HRU.

level, the air flow rate was increased to $51 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ for the second cycle of tests. This adjustment allowed the reactor outlet temperature to match the inlet temperature in about 7 h during the charging process, 3 h faster than with an air flow rate of $34 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$. The increased air flow accelerated the dehydration reaction within the TCES composite material by delivering more heat in a shorter time, thus promoting the reaction of salt hydrates more efficiently. During the discharging process in the second cycle, the peak $T_{\text{HEX,in}}$ and water temperature lift were $34.05 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, with the duration of temperature lift above $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 150 min. Additionally, the increased air flow rate resulted in over a 30 % increase in heat absorbed by the water, underscoring the enhanced system efficiency at higher air velocities. The third and fourth cycles of charging and discharging were conducted at this same air flow rate of

$51 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$, with temperature measurements at various points aligning closely with those from the second cycle. Table 6 summarizes the overall results of these four cycles. From the second to the fourth rounds, slight decreases were noted in several metrics, such as weight changes during charging/discharging, heat absorbed by the TCM during charging, heat released by the TCM during discharging, and heat absorbed by the water flow. This decline was attributed to partial deliquescence within the TCM composite material during the discharge process, which blocked some pores, thus restricting the participation of CaCl_2 in the hydration reaction.

5.3. Economic analysis and levelized cost of energy storage

Based on the experimental results, the technical feasibility of the multi-layer DFHEX-TCES system for domestic space heating has been demonstrated. To further assess its economic viability, a preliminary estimation of the levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES) was conducted. LCOES represents the total cost per unit of useful thermal energy output over the system's lifetime and is calculated as:

$$\text{LCOS} = \frac{C_{\text{cap}} + C_{\text{O\&M}}}{E_{\text{total}}} \quad (13)$$

where C_{cap} is the capital cost of the system, $C_{\text{O\&M}}$ is the total operation and maintenance cost during the system's lifetime, and E_{total} is the cumulative useful thermal energy output.

In this study, the component costs were estimated based on current industrial market prices. Each single-layer packed bed contains approximately 1.5 kg of vermiculite- CaCl_2 composite, and the cost of the composite material together with the metal reactor bed is about £20 per unit. With four packed beds in total, the remaining components—including the reactor casing, heat exchanger, duct fan, insulation, and auxiliary parts—add approximately £500, bringing the total system capital cost to about £580. Assuming a service life of 20 years and 12 charge/discharge cycles per year, the system undergoes 240 cycles in total. Experimental data show that each cycle can deliver approximately

Fig. 17. Dynamic temperature profiles at various measurement points within the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system during four successive cycle tests.

Table 6

Overall performance results of the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system across four consecutive cycles.

Cycle No.	<i>t</i> (min)	\dot{V} (m ³ ·h ⁻¹)	<i>m_i</i> (g)	Δm (g)	Peak ΔT_w (°C)	<i>Q</i> _{TCM,ab} (kJ)	<i>Q</i> _{TCM,re} (kJ)	<i>Q</i> _{w,ab} (kJ)	HRU Recovery efficiency (%)
Discharging (From the fully dried)	300	34	5664	564	5.91		1543	902	
Discharging (From the fully dried)	360	34	5664	654	5.91		1792	1047	57
Cycle 1: charging	600	34	6324	526		1996			61
Cycle 1: discharging	300	34	5814	501	3.52		1353	572	58
Cycle 2: charging	600	51	6316	609		2105			61
Cycle 2: discharging	300	51	5719	606	5		1579	740	57
Cycle 3: charging	600	51	6330	611		2131			61
Cycle 3: discharging	300	51	5732	603	4.95		1573	732	57
Cycle 4: charging	600	51	6335	615		2140			61
Cycle 4: discharging	300	51	5740	602	4.92		1570	732	57

3 kWh of thermal energy, resulting in a cumulative useful energy output of 720 kWh. Annual operation and maintenance costs are estimated at £60, resulting in a lifetime operation and maintenance cost of £1200. Based on these assumptions, the estimated LCOES is approximately £2.5/kWh. While this value is currently around 10 times higher than that of more mature thermal energy storage technologies, it is expected to decrease significantly with scale-up and improvements in system design and manufacturing. This suggests promising potential for mid-to long-term deployment.

6. Conclusions

This study developed a multifunctional water-based thermochemical energy storage (TCES) system setup, conducting both reactor-level and system-level tests to evaluate two different TCES system configurations under various operating conditions. These configurations include one incorporates an internal bare microchannel heat exchanger (IBHEX) and the other employs a detached finned microchannel heat exchanger (DFHEX). Key findings from the study include.

- (1) Both water-based single-layer TCES reactors demonstrated comparable peak water temperature lifts, yet the IBHEX-TCES reactor underperformed in sustaining elevated water temperatures over time. In the high air flow condition (34 m³ h⁻¹), the single-layer DFHEX-TCES reactor with a 6 cm packed bed achieved a peak water temperature lift of 9 °C, which is more than 3 °C higher than at a lower air flow condition and maintained the water temperature above 5 °C for 1.5 h, three times the duration under lower air flow conditions. In contrast, the IBHEX-TCES reactor sustained this temperature lift for only one-third of the DFHEX-TCES duration.
- (2) The IBHEX's embedded bare structure led to limitations in TCM loading capacity, shortened water temperature lift duration, and reduced heat release compared to the DFHEX-TCES one. The direct embedding also increased corrosion risks and extended the time required for filling and replacing TCM, adding to operational complexity.
- (3) The complete single-layer DFHEX-TCES system with fully dried TCM achieved a peak water temperature lift of 6.82 °C, maintaining a water temperature lift above 5 °C for 65 min, albeit with some of the heat offset by warming the incoming air to match the water flow temperature. Successive charging/discharging cycles showed a decline in both the peak water temperature lift (35 %) and the heat absorbed by the water during the discharging process (25 %). These declines are attributed to the limited dehydration from low-temperature charging (90 °C). Notably, the DFHEX did not significantly increase energy consumption, and the system demonstrated stable performance over four charging/discharging cycles without any noticeable degradation.
- (4) Although the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system exhibited a slight decrease in peak water temperature lift compared to the single-layer system, it greatly extended the duration during which the

water temperature exceeded 5 °C. The multilayer DFHEX-TCES system sustained a 5 °C temperature lift for 2.5 h, more than twice the duration achieved by the single-layer configurations. The system performance remained stable during four cycle tests, indicating that the multilayer configuration can reliably extend thermal output duration.

Overall, the DFHEX-TCES reactor outperforms the IBHEX-TCES reactor in terms of output performance and operational simplicity, making it a more viable option for water-based TCES applications. The multilayer DFHEX-TCES system design, despite a marginal reduction in peak temperature lift, markedly enhances thermal output duration, suggesting its feasibility for large-scale applications. Future research will involve developing a full-scale, water-based multilayer DFHEX-TCES system to evaluate its performance in both laboratory and real-world building scenarios, further validating its applicability.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yong Zhang: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ziwei Chen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jianbin Chen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Michele Botarelli:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Yuehong Su:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology. **Saffa Riffat:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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